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Repair and joining of vitrimer carbon fibre reinforced polymers (vCFRPs)

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Introduction

¹Lieber et al., Science, 2011

Leibler and coworkers¹ developed the first epoxy vitrimer in 2011 which had a property unique among thermosets: dynamic covalent bonding.

Without depolymerising, a thermoset can flow, promoting reprocessing and repairability.

This has risen the interest of using vitrimers in the composites community.

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ELSEVIER

New material: vitrimers promise to impact composites

Denis A. Kissounko, Philip Taynton, Chris Kaffer

Strong and durable like thermosets, yet moldable and recyclable like thermoplastics, vitrimers are 'malleable thermosets' which are challenging the status quo in the composites industry. Mallinda, a startup company founded by some of the pioneering inventors of the technology, is developing malleable CFRPs for rapid (30 s) production cycle times.

Some examples of vCFRP

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Epoxy resin with exchangeable disulfide crosslinks to obtain reprocessable, repairable and recyclable fiber-reinforced thermoset composites†

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Contents lists available at ScienceDirect

Carbon

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Reversing fatigue in carbon-fiber reinforced vitrimer composites

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Our work

²Ruiz de Luzuriaga et al., Material Horizons, 2016

³Kamble et al., Carbon, 2022

⁴Mallinda Inc.

Evaluate the following aspects of vCFRP

- I. Manufacturability
- II. Reparability
- III. Joinability

We have studied **four different vitrimers** with different of dynamic bonding nature and different vitrification temperatures

- Epoxy vitrimers with aromatic disulfides² - **VAFD**
- Epoxy vitrimer with transesterification³ - **VAA/TBD**
- Polyimine-based⁴- **V100 / V130**

Evaluating manufacturability

Manual lay up + Autoclave

- 8 plies per sample
- Cured in the autoclave at 7 bar following the temperature cycle defined by supplier/scientific papers

a) DGEBA, AA, TBD

b) DGEBA, AFD

c) V100

d) V130

Viscoelastic experiment

We monitor the storage modulus of the resin over the curing cycle to ensure that the materials are fully cured. This is important when studying healing and repair.

Comparison of mechanical properties

Mechanical properties of small specimens (30 x 3 x 3 mm) tested in 3-point bending.

The three vCFRP show a wide difference in properties going from a more brittle-type failure to a pseudo-ductile type failure

These samples are then used to evaluate reparability and healing properties.

Repair – non localised damage - 3PB

Repair – localised damage - SENB

We use Single Edge Notch Beam (SENB) to measure healing capabilities during translaminar fracture. Crack healing is observed during temperature/pressure is applied. However, the initiation toughness after healing is not fully recovered.

Repair – localised damage - DCB

We use Double Cantilever Beam Test (DCB) to measure healing capabilities in interlaminar fracture.

Example of poor healing (DCB 1):

As manufactured

As healed

Repair – localised damage - DCB

We use Double Cantilever Beam Test (DCB) to measure healing capabilities in interlaminar fracture.

Example of a successful healing (DCB 2):

Repair – localised damage - DCB

During the DCB test, we track the crack opening displacement (δ) and the crack length (a) to measure interlaminar fracture toughness/fracture energy (G_{ic}):

$$G_{Ic} = \frac{3E_{11}w_r^3\delta_r^2}{8a^4} + \frac{3E_{11}w_l^3\delta_l^2}{8a^4}$$

where w is the width of the arms and E_{11} the Young's Modulus in the bending direction

DCB 1 does not recover the properties until we reach the pristine region.

DCB 2 recovers almost the pristine interlaminar fracture energy from early on.

Repair – localised damage - DCB

Preliminary work using DIC to study localised crack healing

Joining

We join two samples by applying heat and pressure: 1 MPa (10 N) and 3 MPa (30 N).

The vitrimer flows and allows for the fibre to intertwine together.

Joined samples are then tested in tension.

Conclusions

- Different vitrimers very different microstructure and mechanical properties. We can reach similar properties to conventional CFRPs
- Repair has been studied by looking at localised and non localised damages.
- We observe some healing in after translaminar and interlaminar fracture.
- Joining can be investigated in the future

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**Thanks for your
attention**

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